

Study of the Historical Process of Turkic Borrowed Words

V. A. Vositov ¹

¹ (DSc), ASIFL

Abstract:

The article analyzes the study of Turkic borrowings by world linguistics, their appearance for certain reasons in English such as direct or indirect ways of communication, socio-political, diplomatic relations, trade and military campaigns with other peoples during the period.

Keywords: Turkic words, borrowed word, assimilated words, thematic groups.

In world linguistics, the problem of Turkic lexical units has been under discussion since the half of the XIX century. Their functional characteristic and pragmatic features on the basis of English material have been in the center of a wide discussion. Now serious work on the phonetic, lexical-semantic, structural-morphological features of Turkic borrowings as a specific phenomenon of a language is of practical importance.

In world linguistics, scientific and theoretical ideas are put forward in the disclosure of phonetic, lexical-semantic, structural-morphological features of Turkic assimilations, in particular, the study of the specific aspects of the historical conditions, structural-morphological, chronological, thematic, phonetic, graphic and lexical-semantic sides of the appearance of Turkic assimilated words in English creates new directions within the framework of modern linguistics. As a result, there has been an improvement in scientific and theoretical views on the study of the causes of the appearance of Turkic borrowings in the English language, chronological, thematic, structural-morphological types, phonetic, graphic and lexical-semantic features.

It is natural for words existed in a language to be borrowed into another language. Because human beings, for certain reasons during their life, borrow words directly or indirectly as a result of their communication with those who communicate in another language. Turkic words also came into

English for reasons such as socio-political, diplomatic relations, trade and military campaigns with other peoples during the period.

Until recently, in Russian English science, insufficient attention was paid to the issue of the contacts of English and Turkish. In textbooks on the lexicology of the English language, Turkic borrowings are also less spoken. Most of the researchers did not give full information about the reasons for the entry of Turkic words into the English language, their assimilation by the people living in England and their phonetic, lexical, grammatical and semantic assimilation. This necessitates the study of this issue.

The process of borrowing words was naturally easy in the countries closely located to each other. E.E.Uzhinin, who did research on the parts of speech and thematic groups of Turkic words adopted into the Cypriot dialect of the new Greek language from the languages of the eastern countries centered around the Ottoman Empire and the Eastern Mediterranean, noted that more words related to the noun category were borrowed into the English language. Among the borrowed words related to the noun category there are those used in everyday life, agriculture, folklore representing 18.9% [6].

At this point, it should be said that borrowed word, barbarism, exotic lexicon can be recognized as a type of foreign word. Because they are all borrowed, and the owner of the receiving language considers as a foreign word, and as a new (neologism) word that has entered from a foreign language. In addition, there are also manual words in the language, which also have the property of loan words. As proof of our opinion, we say that professor N.Ulukov refers to words belonging to foreign languages that are found in the Uzbek language in scientific sources: 1) borrowed words, 2) guide words [5]. The guide words are divided into two types according to the communicative and stylistic functions: 1. Exotic lexicons or exotisms. 2. Introductory words and phrases [7].

From the above points it can be concluded that a loan word is a process of general borrowing through direct and indirect language communication, and an exotic lexicon is a set of concepts that represent this word in the language being borrowed.

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